

Recruitment and Employment Assessment System on the Performance of Mom and Kids Radio Employees Bandung

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Abstract

This study aims to find empirical evidence of the effect of the recruitment system and job appraisal on employee performance at Radio Mom and Kids in Bandung. The research method uses explanatory research methods. The research was conducted on all 34 employees at Radio Mom and Kids. The sampling system uses a saturated sample where all employees are used as the unit of observation. The method of analysis in this study uses multiple linear regression analysis with statistical t test and F test at a significance level of 5%. Data were taken using a questionnaire instrument and interviews. The results showed that the recruitment system had a significant positive effect on employee performance. Job appraisal also has a significant effect on employee performance with a positive relationship direction.

Keywords: *Recruitment System, Job Appraisal, Employee Performance, Radio Mom and Kids.*

INTRODUCTION

The development of technology and the advancement of the business world today requires companies to have employees who are able to achieve high performance. High employee performance makes it easier for the company to accelerate progress and keep abreast of developments in the business world. To achieve this, companies need to select and place employees in the right positions so that their performance can be maximized. Activities that can be carried out to help companies find the right employees are through the implementation of an appropriate recruitment system.

Employees are assets that have a large enough contribution to the development of the company, poor handling by management will hinder the company's goals, it must be realized that employees not only need material but also need proper appreciation and assessment, besides that as a workforce they have thoughts, dignity, desires and hopes that they feel. One aspect of the success of a company's business can be seen from the policies of the leadership of a company in terms of how the recruitment and assessment system is applied by the company.

The need for Human Resources who have the expertise and ability to carry out company plans and goals causes companies to have to plan and develop strategies for procurement and recruitment of employees or often termed as workforce withdrawal. Recruitment is one of the alternatives that the company does to fill job vacancies in the company and to get skilled employees who are able to work in accordance with the wishes and goals of the company. Therefore, the company must recruit employees carefully and thoroughly so that there is little possibility of irregularities in carrying out employee recruitment.

In addition to formulating a strategy in carrying out the recruitment process, the company also requires an assessment of the performance of its employees. Employee performance appraisalThe right approach is not only seen from the results that are done, but also seen from the employee's process in completing his work. Performance is the result of work, the result of a person's entire process in doing his job. Through an appropriate mechanism and work appraisal system, it will encourage employees' work motivation towards achieving high performance.

Radio Mom and Kids is one of the radio stations in Bandung that has been operating since 1999. Since 2012 Radio Mom and Kids has expanded its market and specializes in broadcasting to the segmentation of mothers and children. In the midst of the competition in the broadcasting business, Radio Mom and Kids is required to always be able to provide quality education and broadcasting for the listening community. Therefore, it is necessary to implement an appropriate human resource management system. Through the implementation of the right human resource management system, the company's employees will have integrity and high performance. The implementation of the human resource management system starts from the right employee recruitment system to the work appraisal system that is able to show the achievement of the employee's performance level.

Based on the explanation above, this study aims to determine

1. How does the recruitment system affect the performance of Radio Mom and Kids employees.
2. How does the performance appraisal affect the performance of Radio Mom and Kids employees.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee performance is the result of work and work behavior achieved in completing the tasks and responsibilities given in a certain period of time. Increased employee performance will encourage an increase in company performance in general (Kasmir, 2016: 182). Therefore, it is important for companies to pay attention to the performance of their employees whether they can achieve the targets set. The work results that can be achieved by these employees can be measured through indicators such as: quality of work, quantity of work, timeliness, cost effectiveness, need for supervision, and interpersonal relationships (Kashmir, 2016:18). Many factors can affect the achievement of employee performance. The factors that will be examined in this study are the employee recruitment system and the work appraisal system used.

The recruitment system is a system designed to obtain prospective employees according to the number and terms of the position needed. HR needs can be met from internal and external sources. The recruitment process by combining internal and external sources is intended to cover the weaknesses of each source (Marwansyah, 2010). A properly designed recruitment system allows the company to obtain the required employees both in terms of quantity and quality. So, the company can get employees with the right man on the right job at the right place. If the employee's skills are in accordance with the demands of the job, the employee will be able to maximize his performance. Thus, the right recruitment system can encourage companies to acquire high-performing employees (Wardhana, 2019). Based on this, the research hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H1: There is a significant effect of the recruitment system on employee performance

The work appraisal system is a system used by companies to measure employee performance achievements. An effective work appraisal system is determined by the process, implementation, and methods used. The process in relation to job appraisal is an important factor that can determine the operation of a job appraisal system. The existence of a correct and structured process is able to create a good work appraisal system. In this study, the performance appraisal system will be measured through five stages of the process, namely identify specific performance appraisal goals, establish job expectations, examine work performed, appraise performance, and discuss appraisal with employee (Kurniawan, 2017). A good work appraisal system starting from the process carried out to implementation and the methods used can affect employee performance. The better the work appraisal process, the more measurable the employee's performance will be. So that the company will immediately obtain the right information about the achievement of employee performance. This can encourage the company to improve and design a work appraisal method that is appropriate and acceptable to all employees. Appropriate job appraisal can encourage employee performance improvement (Ulfa, 2018). Based on this, the second research hypothesis is as follows:

H2: There is a significant effect of performance appraisal on employee performance

METHOD

This research was conducted on Mom and Kids Radio, which is located in Bandung, Indonesia. The research method uses descriptive and explanatory methods. The unit of analysis includes all 34 employees. Sampling used a saturated sample where all existing employees were used as respondents. Respondents in this study consisted of 20 men (58.85%) and 14 women (41.18%), most of the respondents were in the age range between 26-35 year (32.35%). most of the respondents have an undergraduate education (35.29%), and most of the respondents have a working period of 1-5 years (38.24%).

Recruitment system variables measured through indicators of internal sources and external sources. Job appraisal is measured through the indicators of identify specific performance appraisal goals, establish job expectations, examine work performed, appraise performance, and discuss appraisal with employee. Employee performance variables are measured through indicators of work quality, quantity of work, timeliness, cost effectiveness, need for supervision, and relationships between individuals.

Data were collected through interviews and questionnaires using a Likert scale with 31 question items, consisting of 9 items of recruitment system variables, 10 items of job appraisal variables, and 12 items of employee performance variables. The questionnaire used to retrieve the data has gone through validity and reliability tests. The analytical method in this study uses multiple linear regression analysis by first testing the classical assumption. Statistics use the F test for the research model and t test to test the hypothesis at a significance level of 5%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis of Recruitment System Variables

Based on the score of respondents' responses to the internal source indicator, the mean score of 3.45 is included in the good category. The highest mean score of 3.88 in the statement that the company recruits employees from internal sources by means of internal mutations or moving employees to the part that is needed, so that employees do not need to adapt to the company environment. The lowest mean score is 3.15 on the statement that the company recruits employees from internally adjusted to the job specifications that are currently needed.

Based on the score of respondents' responses to external source indicators, it shows that the mean score of 3.49 is included in the good category. The highest mean score of 3.79 in the leadership statement always shows an attitude of responsibility for each job. The lowest mean score of 3.21 in the leader's statement can provide a clear picture of the work and is easily understood by employees.

The following presents the results of the recapitulation of the respondent's response scores from each indicator on the recruitment system variable, as follows:

Table 1. Respondents' Responses Regarding Recruitment System Variables

No	Indicator	Actual Score	Ideal Score	% score	Mean Score	Category
1	Internal Source	586	850	68.94	3.45	Good
2	External Source	475	680	69.85	3.49	Good
Total/Average		1061	1530	69.35	3.47	Good

Source: Data processed

Descriptive Analysis of Job Appraisal Variables

The respondent's response score on the Identify Specific Performance Appraisal Goals indicator shows a mean score of 3.35 which is included in the fairly good category. The highest mean score of 3.74 on the company's statement to identify the company's goals. The lowest mean score of 2.97 on the company's statement to identify the established performance appraisal system.

The respondent's response score on the establish job expectations indicator shows a mean score of 3.76 which is included in the good category. The highest mean score of 3.79 in the company's statement determines the criteria or factors as a measure of performance appraisal. The lowest mean score of 3.74 on the company's statement sets the standard of performance appraisal for each position function in the company.

The respondent's response score on the examine work performed indicator shows a mean score of 3.01 which is included in the fairly good category. The highest mean score of 3.03 on the company's statement to examine employee performance against the criteria or factors of performance assessment. The lowest mean score is 3.00 on the statement that the company checks the conformity of performance standards with performance assessment criteria or factors.

The respondent's response score on the appraise performance indicator shows a mean score of 3.04 which is included in the fairly good category. The highest mean score of 3.12 on the company's statement through managers in each division assessing employee performance as a whole. The lowest mean score of 2.97 on the company's statement through managers in each division assessing employee performance according to the specified period such as monthly, quarterly, semester, and yearly.

The respondent's response score on the discuss appraisal with employee indicator shows a mean score of 3.07 which is included in the fairly good category. The highest mean score of 3.18 in the company's statement through managers in each division communicates the results of employee performance appraisals to all employees in the company as a form of evaluation. The lowest mean score is 2.97 on the company's statement through managers in each division analyzing the results of employee performance appraisals.

The following presents the results of the recap of the respondent's response scores from each indicator on the work appraisal variable, as follows:

Table 2. Respondents' Responses to Job Appraisal Variables

No	Indicator	Actual Score	Ideal Score	%	Mean Score	Category
1	Identify Specific Performance Appraisal Goals	228	340	67.06	3.35	Pretty good
2	Establish Job Expectations	256	340	75.29	3.76	Good
3	Examine Work Performed	205	340	60.29	3.01	Pretty good
4	Appraise Performance	207	340	60.88	3.04	Pretty good
5	Discuss Appraisal with Employee	209	340	61.47	3.07	Pretty good
Total/Average		1105	1700	65.00	3.25	Pretty good

Source: Data processed

Descriptive Analysis of Employee Performance Variables

The work quality indicator shows a mean score of 3.06 which is included in the fairly good category. The highest mean score of 3.12 means that employees are able to complete work above the standards set by the company. The lowest mean score of 3.00 means that employees are able to complete the work in accordance with the targets set by the company.

The respondent's response score on the work quantity indicator shows a mean score of 3.47 which is included in the good category. The highest mean score of 3.79 means that employees are able to complete all the work that is their responsibility. The lowest mean score of 3.15 means that the amount of work that is the responsibility of employees is still in a reasonable stage.

The respondent's response score on the timeliness indicator shows a mean score of 3.09 which is included in the fairly good category. The highest mean score of 3.18 means that employees always manage time at work well so that all work can be completed. The lowest mean score of 3.00 means that employees always complete work on time.

The respondent's response score on the cost effectiveness indicator shows a mean score of 3.74 which is included in the good category. The highest mean score of 3.76 means that the organizational resources provided to employees are sufficient to support the work. The lowest mean score of 3.71 means that employees can manage the available organizational resources well.

The respondent's response score on the indicator of need for supervision shows a mean score of 3.46 which is included in the good category. The highest mean score of 3.79 means that employees have high initiative in completing work. The lowest mean score of 3.12 means that employees are able to face and find their own solutions to every problem at work.

The respondent's response score on the supervisory needs indicator shows a mean score of 3.50 which is included in the fairly good category. The highest mean score of 3.85 means that employees have a good relationship with their superiors. The lowest mean score is 3.15 that employees have good relations with other employees in the company.

In the following, the results of the recapitulation of the respondent's response scores from each indicator on the employee performance variable are presented as follows:

Table 3. Recapitulation of Respondents' Responses Regarding Employee Performance Variables

No	Indicator	Actual Score	Ideal Score	%	Mean Score	Category
1	Work quality	208	340	61.18	3.06	Pretty good
2	Working Quantity	236	340	69.41	3.47	Good
3	Punctuality	210	340	61.76	3.09	Pretty good
4	Cost Effectiveness	254	340	74.71	3.74	Good
5	Supervision Needs	235	340	69.12	3.46	Good
6	Relationships Between Individuals	238	340	70.00	3.50	Good
Total/Average		1381	2040	67.70	3.38	Pretty good

Source: Data processed

Test Results of the Effect of Recruitment and Job Assessment Systems on Employee Performance

The results of testing the research model can be seen in the following table.

Table4. The Results of Estimates Multiple Linear Regression Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	p-value	
(Constant)	0.173	0.317	0.547	0.588	
Recruitment System	0.454	0.125	3.634	0.001	Sign
Job Appraisal	0.477	0.123	3.880	0.001	Sign
R-Squared	0.618				
Adj. R-Squared	0.594				
F-Statistics	25.098				
Prob. F	0.000				
☐	0.05				

a Predictors: (Constant):Recruitment System, Job Appraisal

b Dependent Variables:Employee performance

Based on the table above, it can be explained that the recruitment system has a significant influence on employee performance with a p-value of 0.001 with a positive relationship direction. This means that if the recruitment system is right then the company will be able to get employees who are able to achieve high performance. Job appraisal also has a positive relationship and has a significant effect on employee performance with a p-value of 0.001. This also shows that the right work appraisal system can show the performance that employees can achieve. Recruitment system variables and job appraisal can affect employee performance by 59.4%. The recruitment process at Radio Mom and Kids, namely by taking human resources from within and from outside the company, has been empirically proven to have an effect on employee performance. Recruitment from within the company provides opportunities for existing employees to get promotions and fill job vacancies as a form of effective performance appraisal results. Recruitment from outside the company provides an opportunity for the entry of new ideas. For companies that must be a concern in internal recruitment is that the recruitment must be based on the required job specifications. Meanwhile, in the external recruitment system, it is expected that Leaders can provide a clear picture of the work and are easily understood by employees.

The results of this study imply that it is important for companies to pay attention to the right recruitment system because it can affect the achievement of employee performance in the future. In general, the research results show that the implementation of the recruitment system is running effectively with the aim of creating healthy internal competition as a stimulus for improving employee performance. The results of this study are in line with research findings from Suryani (2014), Badriyah (2015), Aziz (2017), Wardhana (2019), Saputra (2020), and Purba (2021) who found that recruitment systems and processes affect employee performance.

Employee performance appraisal as measured through the process identify specific performance appraisal goals, establish job expectations, examine work performed, appraise performance, and discuss appraisal with employee empirically proven to have an effect on employee performance. In general, the performance appraisal process on Radio Mom and Kids it's been going pretty well. The results of the study indicate that there are several things whose implementation has not been optimal, namely: the company must identify the established performance appraisal system, maximize the setting of performance appraisal standards for each position function, conduct an examination of the conformity of performance standards with performance appraisal criteria or factors, conduct performance appraisals according to the stipulated period, and must analyze the results of employee performance appraisals.

The results of this study imply that it is important for companies to pay attention to the appropriate and acceptable work appraisal process because it will affect the achievement of employee performance. In general, the research results show that the work appraisal process has been running effectively and can encourage employee performance improvement. The results of this study are in line with research findings from Rani (2015), Indria (2015), Tangkuman (2015), Prasasti (2016), Ulfa (2018, and Wilandari (2021) who found that performance appraisal had a positive effect on employee performance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the performance of employees at Radio Mom and Kids can be predicted through the recruitment system and job appraisal system used. The recruitment system measured through internal and external sources has a significant influence on employee performance with a positive relationship direction. This shows that the right recruitment system can encourage employee performance improvement. Work appraisal as measured through indicators identify specific performance appraisal goals, establish job expectations, examine work performed, appraise performance, and discuss appraisal with employee also has a significant effect on employee performance with a positive relationship direction. This shows that a good job appraisal can encourage an increase in employee performance.

The results of this study have limitations, especially in terms of the unit of observation and the limited number of independent variables identified. Future research should be carried out within the scope of a larger unit of observation, namely by adding respondents from a wider object of observation. Independent variables can be developed by adding other variables in the human resource management function which are identified to affect employee performance.

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